

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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Modern trends in educational psychology and psychology of education.

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Abstract. Educational psychology is not general psychology, not child psychology, and not pedagogy; it is a discipline that connects psychology with pedagogy, leading from psychology to pedagogy. In fact, from this moment on, psychology was recognized as a key area of knowledge that determines the scientifically based training of specialists in the field of human education, psychologists and teachers.

Keywords: education, human development, educational space, pedagogical research, learning process, pedagogy, psychology.

First and foremost, it is important to understand the learning process that occurs to facilitate proper teaching. Learning occurs when there is a greater or lesser change in behavior as a result of experience. Given this concept, the role of the teacher is to provide learning experiences inside or outside the classroom so that learning occurs. Peterson and Piaget explained learning as a process that occurs through assimilation, accommodation, and equilibration. According to Piaget, learning occurs through schemas.

Schemas allow individuals to make connections with the information they receive. Assimilation is the process of absorbing new experiences from the environment and adding them to previous experiences. Accommodation is the integration of new experiences with old ones and the formation of new ideas and ways of thinking as a result of this integration. Assimilation occurs when individuals internalize information, while accommodation results in the creation of new information. Once assimilation and accommodation occurs, the individual is now in a state of equilibrium where the processed information becomes part of his or her schema.

The learning process as described above consists of three stages: input, processing, and output. The process of human cognition is similar to how a computer processes information. Input occurs when the senses receive data from the environment. The data we perceive can be the shape, size, texture, color, and other

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qualities of an object. During the processing stage, a specific image of the object will be recognized. The object is further abstracted by recognizing the given qualities of the object. Concept formation then occurs when a name is assigned to the object. If the processed information is new, a new concept is created and stored in memory for future use.

The output occurs when people try to express the concept. Having understood the learning process, it is necessary to turn to the modern views on the effective learning process explained by Bernardo.

1. The learner is assumed to be an information processor. The mind has a diverse system of operations similar to the procedures of a computer program;

2. Learning is active and constructive. Learners do not just perceive information; they engage in activities that involve the processing of information. rather, they construct their own knowledge and skills by actively processing the information they encounter in a variety of situations.

3. Learning is cumulative. Students always bring a range of relevant knowledge and skills to any new learning situation; it is never tabula rasa for the student. Learners use their prior knowledge to structure and constrain future learning.

4. Learning is self-regulated. The teacher does not have complete control over the learning process. Rather, it is the student who takes the necessary steps to learn, monitors the learning process, provides self-feedback and evaluates his or her performance, and maintains concentration and motivation.

5. Learning is goal-oriented. Learning is best facilitated when the learner has a clear sense of the goals of learning, especially when students set their own goals.

6. Learning is embedded in social/cultural practice. People learn by participating in social practices and events.

7. Learning is individual. The results and specific learning process vary among students. It is important to note that psychology in its holistic content, and not in a discrete representation (exclusively educational psychology) has become an integral part of the processes of learning, education and human development, which was manifested in the formation of a special direction - pedagogy (the study of child development).

Now, in connection with the processes of globalization and integration of knowledge, we often talk not about educational psychology, but about "Educational

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Psychology" as a field that describes the whole variety of psychological changes that occur with a person included in the educational system (at the level of his personality, interpersonal relationships, professionalization, intellectual development, etc.).

On the one hand, educational psychology is certainly a part of educational psychology. On the other hand, has it dissolved in a new, broader research space? Or does it still retain its special place in the mainstream of educational psychology. It would seem that the answer is obvious - the changes that have already occurred have led to the creation of new approaches and concepts for organizing the educational space, assessing its potential and the possibility of its use from the point of view of psychology. At the same time, the originality of educational psychology is determined by the focus on the psychology of teaching and education, as well as on the psychology of the teacher.

Thus, today this continuity has developed, but it is not entirely obvious. Any transformation takes time to understand the changes taking place. And, perhaps, today we are not ready to recognize educational psychology as the successor of educational psychology. Fundamental principles of psychological and pedagogical research, principles of scientific psychology and philosophy that determine the formation and development of personality in the educational environment are important.

At present, the most generalized characteristics of scientific works in this area are attempts to present and consider the educational environment as a space for human self-determination, where the student in the educational situation is in a reflexive relationship, the center of which is the formation of his individual reality. The core of psychological and pedagogical anthropology is knowledge about human psychology as a doctrine of subjective reality, human developmental psychology as a doctrine of the development of subjective reality at the stages of ontogenesis and pedagogical psychology as a doctrine of the formation of human subjective reality in educational processes."

Thus, educational psychology is an integral part of psychological and pedagogical anthropology (anthropology of education), which develops the problems of sustainable development and changes in the positions of educational subjects and their constituent communities at key stages of socialization and maturation, individual trajectories of self-education and self-development. In fact,

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educational psychology defines the fundamental psychological foundations of lifelong education. In general, to solve the problems of psychological theory in the field of education, it is necessary to .

Thus, the main directive in the psychology of learning and teaching is emphasized to be the improvement of teaching or instruction in order to facilitate better assimilation of the material. The ultimate goal of informing students is for them to love learning and to gain the desire to become independent and continue learning. It is also important to consider that individual learning varies for each student, and the role of the teacher is to provide authentic learning experiences to achieve better academic performance for the majority of students. It is commonly said that a bad teacher talks, an average teacher explains, a good teacher demonstrates, and a great teacher empowers. To empower students, teachers must use all effective teaching tools. References: 1. Anderson, L. M., et al. (1995). Educational Psychology for Teachers: Reforming Our Courses, Rethinking Our Roles; 2. Bernardo, A. (1997). Creating Powerful Learning Environments; 3. Caluag, A. (2002). The Psychology of Learning and Teaching. Ateneo de Manila University.

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List of used literature:

1. Азимова Н. Э., Насимова З. И. Маънавий-маърифий ишлар жараёнида бўлажак касб таълими ўқитувчисини тарбиялаш методикаси //psixologiya Учредители: Бухарский государственный университет. – №. 3. – С. 129-134.
2. Azimova N. E. Problems of development of new pedagogical technologies of training of teachers of professional education and their introduction into the educational and educational process //Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1-3.
3. Azimova N. E. Formation of National and Ideological Education of Students is an Integral Part of the Learning Process. – 2021.
4. Azimova N. E. A financially independent higher education institution is the foundation of our future //Scientific progress. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 130-134.
5. Azimova N. E. et al. Youth Is Moving Force of Civil Society //Eastern European Scientific Journal. – 2019. – №. 1.
6. Азимова Н. Э. Технология духовно-нравственного воспитания преподавателя профессионального образования в процессе обучения //Молодой ученый. – 2011. – №. 5-2. – С. 117-118.
7. Азимова Н. Э. Роль профессионального педагога в подготовке гармонично развитой личности //Международный журнал гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2018. – №. 5-1.
8. Азимова Н. Э., Насимова З. И. К. Важные особенности человеческого образования в семье //Academy. – 2020. – №. 5 (56).
9. Азимова Н. Э., Элибоева Л. С. Некоторые аспекты повышения уровня экологической культуры //Наука, техника и образование. – 2019. – №. 1 (54).